

Hardware Generators with Chisel

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Abstract—Most digital hardware is described in hardware description languages, such as VHDL and (System)Verilog. These languages provide limited programming models for hardware construction despite receiving regular updates and extensions. Chisel defines itself as a hardware construction language, which means it shall permit more than the mere description of digital circuits. However, programmatic hardware generation is not new. Scripting languages like Perl generate VHDL or Verilog code from sources like Excel spreadsheets. Chisel, embedded in the general-purpose language Scala, lends itself to writing hardware generators in that language. We consider this Chisel-Scala ecosystem an ideal starting point for programming hardware generators and illustrate this point with examples using various programming models. We are confident that proven technologies from the software development world can be leveraged in the hardware design domain to improve hardware designers’ productivity to build the next billion transistor chips.

Index Terms—hardware generation, open-source hardware, and open-source digital design tools.

I. INTRODUCTION

As currently used hardware description languages (HDLs), such as VHDL and (System)Verilog, are not expressive enough to write generators, hardware designers have resorted to using other (software) languages, such as Perl, Python, or Java to “generate” hardware [27], [25]. In these cases, the generators spill out files in the target language. This is a brittle, error-prone approach. One apparent issue is that the HDL code is represented as strings in the generator language on which syntax checks are not performed [18], [5]. This complicates not only the maintenance of the generators but also upgrading them, for example, to newer, more expressive versions of their target language. Hardware construction languages mitigate these issues with improved expressiveness and extensive checks through compiler-like back-ends and spilling out simple Verilog code for synthesis [4], [3].

Let us consider an example from one of the authors: Before using Chisel, we taught digital design with VHDL. One challenge for the students is to display a binary number in binary-coded decimal (BCD) on a 7-segment display. A simple way to convert a binary number into a BCD number is to use a table that, for a two-decimal digit display, has 100 entries. This challenge calls for automation (scripting), so we provided the students with a Java program that generates the table in VHDL. That program was around 100 lines of code sprinkled with strings containing VHDL code. The code’s core, generating the table, was just six lines. Solving the same problem with Chisel

and Scala is four lines of code. Furthermore, that code is now part of the hardware project in the target hardware construction language.

This paper argues for using Chisel and Scala as a hardware generator language to reduce development and debugging time. The paper provides several successful examples of how combining different programming models in Scala enables and simplifies the definition of highly flexible generators. We believe that this strategy is only in its infancy. We can imagine that future hardware engineers, who have also been trained in classic software development, will explore the domain of hardware generators in ways not yet imaginable. We hope this paper illustrates this domain’s potential and inspires further research efforts. Our main contribution is the exploration and exemplification of hardware generators written in Chisel and Scala.

This paper is organized into eight sections. The following section gives background information on the Chisel hardware construction language. Section III starts the topic by describing simple examples of hardware generation code. Section IV describes the concept of Chisel functions to generate hardware. Section V discusses using object-oriented features in hardware description. Section VI takes functions as first-class language elements to use in functional programming to write flexible hardware generators. Finally, Section VII presents related work, and Section VIII concludes the paper.

II. CHISEL

Chisel is a domain-specific language embedded in Scala meant for the description of digital circuits [4]. Chisel’s embedding in a general-purpose programming language enables the use of powerful language features, including type parameterization and elements of the object-oriented and functional paradigms, to describe hardware generators instead of just the hardware itself. This, in turn, enables the creation of complex hardware designs more efficiently than with traditional HDLs.

The feature of Chisel being embedded in Scala is also visible through its execution mode. Chisel is a Scala library, and using this library when executing the Scala program generates a digital circuit. This execution of Scala code during the generation of digital hardware can be considered as an additional step in the compilation pipeline from a hardware description to the bit-stream for an FPGA or the masks for the ASIC production. This additional step in the pipeline is called

“elaboration”. The elaboration step executes all the magic to implement parameterizable hardware generators by building a graph of hardware elements and the wires connecting them.

The generator code is part of the hardware description; only a simple build script is needed to execute the Chisel code. One of the authors had a project where three VHDL files needed to be generated (by a Java program). He received several complaints that the project was incomplete due to missing VHDL files and could not be synthesized. This issue cannot happen when the generator code is part of the hardware description code and not an external script.

III. SIMPLE EXAMPLES

We begin our discussion of generators with a handful of simple examples, which may not be exciting for an advanced programmer, but are practical and save development (and debugging) time.

A. Table Generation

Compile-time-generated tables are useful for expressing combinational logic or describing a read-only memory (ROM). Such tables can be described as initialization functions of vectors or arrays or with a switch/case statement, depending on availability in the target language. Although the traditional HDLs support the declaration and initialization of array-type constants, the associated syntax in VHDL is verbose [11, Chap. 4]. In contrast, the options for advanced initialization functions appear limited in (System)Verilog¹ [10, Sec. 9.9.1]. Scala enables a more flexible table generation in Chisel. The following example code shows the BCD generation, as mentioned in the introduction:

```
val table = Wire(Vec(100, UInt(8.W)))
for (i <- 0 until 100) {
  table(i) := (((i/10)<<4) + i%10).U
}
```

B. Assembler

Generating static code for an embedded processor, such as a boot program, is a common use case in digital design. The traditional approach involves running an assembler for the target processor, generating a binary file, and reading this binary file in the HDL to generate a ROM in hardware. With Scala, writing the assembler and assembling a boot program for hardware generation in one language is relatively easy. We have implemented two small utility processors, Lipsi [22] and Leros [24], and have written the assembler that generates the ROMs for the processor as Chisel Vecs in just a few lines of Scala code.²

¹Small experiments of ours suggest that some compilers fail to generate tables for iterative patterns that reference previously set array elements.

²See as an example: <https://github.com/schoeberl/lipsi/blob/cbd3131cd058019104a8ddc83c1a9e4e103e4a96/src/main/scala/lipsi/util/Assembler.scala>

C. Register Address Mapping

A common hardware generation practice for large systems is automatically generating memory-mapped configuration registers from a specification file (e.g., XML, JSON). The specification file defines the registers, including their memory-mapped address, size, sub-fields, and access modes (read-only, read-write, write-only). This file is often created and modified using a GUI that visually represents the registers’ structure or derived from a standardized IP specification scheme, such as IP-XACT [1]. A script (e.g., Perl, Python, etc.) is then used to parse the specification file and generate the corresponding HDL code (VHDL or Verilog) and software header files for register definition and documentation.

This automation ensures consistency in the HDL code, software headers, and documentation, significantly reducing the potential for manual coding errors and discrepancies. Moreover, this approach enhances maintainability since any changes to the specification file can be propagated to all generated outputs quickly. On the other hand, this approach is often based on custom ad-hoc scripts. This lack of a unified generation environment may introduce additional complexity for the maintenance of the scripts. Chisel addresses these challenges by providing a high-level design environment integrated within Scala, allowing the generation to be part of the design.

IV. FUNCTIONS

Functions executed during elaboration that return hardware components are at the heart of Chisel hardware generators. These functions provide a powerful and flexible way to describe reusable logic, facilitating modular and scalable design. Functions in Chisel can be a lightweight alternative to Modules, allowing designers to create hardware without the overhead of defining a class. Furthermore, functions can be used as parameters for higher-order functions to allow functional programming to generate hardware, as explained later.

The concept of using functions as a way to encapsulate reusable logic is not unique to Chisel. Both VHDL and (System)Verilog provide similar features [11, Chap. 4] [10, Chap. 10], albeit only for purely combinational functions. In both languages, the structure of a function resembles a component declaration with inputs and outputs followed by a body of statements, defining its logic, ending with a return statement, or assigning some values to the function outputs. This means VHDL functions and procedures resemble processes, while (System)Verilog functions and tasks resemble always (or always_comb) blocks. Although the table generation use case described above requires defining a function in VHDL, the particular function is not synthesized.

In Chisel, a function can generate combinational and sequential logic (registers). For example, the following circuit detects a signal’s rising edge by comparing its current value with the one from the last clock cycle (the delayed value):

```
def rising(v: Bool) = v & !RegNext(v)
```

Listing 1 shows a slightly more complex definition for the function regPipeline, which creates a register pipeline

```

def regPipeline[T <: Data](input: T,
  pipeDepth: Int, init: T): T = {
  if (pipeDepth <= 0) {
    val ret = input
    ret
  } else {
    val pipeReg = RegInit(
      VecInit(Seq.fill(pipeDepth)(init)))
    val ret = pipeReg(0)
    pipeReg(pipeDepth - 1) := input
    for (i <- 0 until pipeDepth - 1) {
      pipeReg(i) := pipeReg(i + 1)
    }
    ret
  }
}

```

Listing 1. A function returning a pipeline of generic type registers with specified depth and initial values.

that delays the input signal by a specified number of cycles (`pipeDepth`). This is particularly useful for pipelining circuits where certain signals must be delayed by several clock cycles determined during hardware generation. The function takes an input signal of type `T`, a pipeline depth, and an initial value for all the pipeline registers. The function forwards the input signal if the pipeline depth is zero or less. Having a single function that can pipeline a generic type `T` (including aggregates such as `Vec` and `Bundle`) showcases the concept of code reusability and flexibility offered by Chisel-based hardware generators.

The code in Listing 1 is written in an imperative style (with a loop iterating over the sequence of registers). However, with Scala’s functional programming features, we can rewrite the loop by using the higher-order function `foldLeft`:

```

def regPipeline[T <: Data](input: T,
  depth: Int, init: T): T = {
  (0 until depth).foldLeft(input) {
    case (acc, _) => RegNext(acc, init)
  }
}

```

In addition to generating single outputs, Chisel functions can return multiple outputs using a Scala tuple. The following function generates a circuit that detects an input signal’s rising and falling edges. The function encapsulates both detection mechanisms and returns the detections as a Scala tuple.

```

def edges(v: Bool): (Bool, Bool) = {
  val delayedV = RegNext(v)
  val rising = signal & !delayedV
  val falling = !signal & delayedV
  (rising, falling)
}

```

In summary, Chisel functions are a powerful tool that provides a lightweight way to create parameterized hardware. Functions can be used instead of small modules.

V. OBJECT ORIENTED PROGRAMMING

Scala is a fully object-oriented programming language. Therefore, we can make use of abstraction, polymorphism,

inheritance, and encapsulation when writing flexible hardware generators.

Abstraction allows hardware designers to focus on high-level design without worrying about low-level implementation details. By using abstract classes and traits, we can define generic hardware interfaces that can be specialized by concrete implementations. A simple example of the role of abstraction is to use an abstract class to represent the interface of a generic FIFO. Then, different implementations (e.g., a bubble FIFO, a memory-based FIFO, or others) can be provided, as exemplified in [23].

Generics are a concept in programming languages to write reusable code that can operate on different data types. The data type itself is the generic parameter. Generics are inherent to Scala (and therefore Chisel) and supported by the underlying JVM through type erasure.³ Similar concepts have been available in the traditional HDLs, VHDL and SystemVerilog, since 2008 [11] and 2005 [9], respectively. We can use generics to provide types for general hardware structures. For example, the Chisel ready/valid interface (`Decoupled`) has a generic parameter for the data type wrapped into the handshake interface. Both the register pipeline and the FIFO examples above also rely on generics to work for any data type.

Inheritance allows for the creation of new hardware modules based on existing ones. It is a key component of Chisel as any user-defined module extends the base class `Module` and inherits all its members and methods, which can later be overridden or extended as needed. It is also useful for creating variations of a hardware component that extend a common interface, probably as an abstract class, with minimal additional code. Again, constructing different types of FIFOs with some shared, common logic is a good example of this.⁴

Encapsulation in Chisel is handled in the same manner as for any other Scala class. Each module encapsulates its internal hardware state and logic, exposing only the necessary interfaces (e.g., through its IO bundle). By default, Scala makes all `val` or `var` fields declared in the module’s main constructor body `public`, meaning they are visible outside the class. However, the values of internal registers, wires, and logic within a module are not readable or writable from the outside, aligning with the principles of encapsulation.

VI. FUNCTIONAL PROGRAMMING

As a next step, we can use functional programming and pass functions as parameters to higher-order functions to generate hardware. We start with a simple example of representing an adder in a Chisel function and using the Scala method `reduce()` to sum a sequence of values:

```

def add(a: UInt, b: UInt): UInt = a + b
val sum = vec.reduce(add)

```

First, we define the hardware for the adder in function `add`. The vector of values (Chisel type `Vec`) is located in `vec`. The

³https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Generics_in_Java

⁴See: <https://github.com/freechipsproject/ip-contributions/tree/100105624274052c7174d74fae15605d951190c4/src/main/scala/chisel/lib/fifo>

method `reduce()` iterates over a collection and combines all its elements with a binary operation to produce a single result, starting with the first two elements and proceeding with the remaining elements one at a time. We provide the function to combine two elements as a parameter to `reduce`, in our case `add`, which returns an adder. The resulting hardware is a chain of adders computing the sum of the elements of vector `vec`.

Instead of defining the (simple) `add` function, we can use the Scala wildcard “`_`” to represent the two operands and provide an equivalent, anonymous function:

```
val sum = vec.reduce(_ + _)
```

With this one-liner, we have generated a chain of adders. However, for the sum function, a chain is not ideal; a tree will have a shorter combinational delay. Thus, if we do not trust the synthesis tool to rearrange our adder chain, we can use Chisel’s `reduceTree` method to generate a tree of adders instead:

```
val sum = vec.reduceTree(_ + _)
```

A. Finding the Minima

As a more elaborate example, we build a circuit to find the minimum value in a `Vec` collection of values. We use an anonymous function called a *function literal* in Scala to express this circuit. The syntax for a function literal is parameters in parentheses, followed by a `=>`, followed by the function body:

```
(param) => function body
```

The function literal for the minimum function uses two parameters `x` and `y` and returns a multiplexer (`Mux`) that compares the two parameters and returns the smaller value. We can describe the search function in one line of Chisel code:

```
val min = vec.reduceTree((x, y) =>
  Mux(x < y, x, y))
```

Let us extend this circuit to return not only the minimal value from the `vec` but also its position (index) in the `vec`. For convenience, we define the bundle `Two` to hold the value and the index. We declare the `vecTwo` `Vec` that can hold these bundles and connect them in a loop to the original input and the index within the `Vec`, as shown in Listing 2.

We again pass a function literal to the `reduceTree` method of `vecTwo`, comparing the value field within the bundle and returning the multiplexer for the complete bundle. Value `res` points to the bundle with the minimum value and its position.

As a more advanced variation of the minimum search circuit, we can use more Scala features to avoid creating the bundle. We use a tuple to represent both values. Listing 3 shows the application of a chain of functions to the original sequence. Chaining functions is a typical pattern in functional programming. This pattern can also be seen as a pipeline of operations.

The first function (`zipWithIndex`) transforms the sequence of `UInts` to a sequence of tuples, where the first element is

```
// Parameters n and w defined by the
  encapsulating class
class Two extends Bundle {
  val v = UInt(w.W)
  val idx = UInt(8.W)
}

val vecTwo = Wire(Vec(n, new Two()))
for (i <- 0 until n) {
  vecTwo(i).v := vec(i)
  vecTwo(i).idx := i.U
}

val res = vecTwo.reduceTree((x, y) =>
  Mux(x.v < y.v, x, y))

val minVal = res.v
val minIdx = res.idx
```

Listing 2. The code for the minimum search, including the index (only the essential part).

```
val resFun = vec.zipWithIndex
  .map(x => (x._1, x._2.U))
  .reduce((x, y) =>
    (Mux(x._1 < y._1, x._1, y._1),
     Mux(x._1 < y._1, x._2, y._2)))

val minVal = resFun._1
val minIdx = resFun._2
```

Listing 3. Using tuples for the minimum search.

the unchanged `UInt` and the second element is the index value within the `Vec` as a Scala `Int`. Generally, a `zip` function merges two sequences (zips them) into a single one containing the two elements as tuples. The next function maps the tuples of a Chisel `UInt` and a Scala `Int` to tuples of two Chisel `UInts`. Finally, the `reduce` function generates the multiplexer chain to find the minimum in the generated sequence by comparing elements two at a time and returning a tuple of two Chisel `UInts`.

The whole functional expression returns hardware with Chisel types only but uses a Scala `Vector` to hold intermediate results. This prevents us from using the `reduceTree` method, which is available for Chisel `Vecs` only. To keep using `reduceTree`, the following solution uses a Chisel `MixedVec` instead of a Scala tuple. A `MixedVec` is similar to a Scala tuple as it can have different types at different positions. Therefore, it cannot function directly as input to a multiplexer, but we can use it as an indexable collection during hardware generation.

```
val scalaVector = vec.zipWithIndex
  .map(x => MixedVecInit(x._1, x._2.U))
val resFun2 = VecInit(scalaVector)
  .reduceTree((x, y) =>
    Mux(x(0) < y(0), x, y))

val minVal = resFun2(0)
val minIdx = resFun2(1)
```

In the above example, we create a Scala Vector of the values with their indices wrapped in MixedVecs. We then convert the Scala Vector into a Chisel Vec and perform a tree-based reduction. Another benefit of this version is that we have only one multiplexer, which selects between two Chisel MixedVecs. The result in `resFun2` is a MixedVec with two elements, accessed with an index, like a “normal” Vec.

B. Arbitration

Combining features described in the previous sections lets us easily construct more advanced circuits. For example, suppose we wish to perform arbitration between n components with ready/valid interfaces. In that case, we can build an arbitration tree out of 2-to-1 arbiters with the `reduceTree` method and output the result to a single ready/valid interface as follows. We need a function `arbitrate` to arbitrate between two requests.

```
class Arbiter[T <: Data](n: Int, private val
  gen: T) extends Module {
  val io = IO(new Bundle {
    val in = Flipped(Vec(n, new
      DecoupledIO(gen)))
    val out = new DecoupledIO(gen)
  })
  // Definition of 'arbitrate' goes here
  io.out <> io.in.reduceTree((a, b) =>
    arbitrate(a, b))
}
```

As an initial solution, we can build a priority-based arbitration. A simple solution results in a purely combinational circuit. However, the ready/valid interface prohibits combinational paths between a ready and a valid signal, thus requiring registers for those signals and the incoming data. The listing of that arbitration circuit can be found in [23].

The initial arbitration circuit gives priority to the first input. To avoid this domination, we must introduce state to remember which of the two inputs won the arbitration the last time. We assume that if the 2-to-1 arbiter is fair, this also results in a fair arbitration scheme on a balanced tree.

Listing 4 shows the fair 2-to-1 arbitration circuit. The arbiter contains one register for the data `regData` and one state register `regState`. To be fair, the arbiter switches between two idle states (`idleA` and `idleB`) when there is no request. Each of the two idle states accepts only one of the inputs. When a request is accepted, the arbiter stores the incoming data and switches to one of the full states (`hasA` or `hasB`). When the consumer of the output accepts the data, the arbiter switches back to the idle state of the opposite input, i.e., `hasA` switches back to `idleB`. Note that with a single data register, the arbiter can only be ready for one of the two inputs. To allow being ready for both inputs and switching priority, we would need a second data register to handle the case when both inputs are valid in the same clock cycle.

C. Software-defined IO

A prior work of ours explored the potential for using Chisel to generate Verilog code for coarse-grained reconfigurable arrays (CGRAs) from descriptions in a high-level XML-based

```
object State extends ChiselEnum {
  val idleA, idleB, hasA, hasB = Value
}

def arbitrate(a: DecoupledIO[T],
  b: DecoupledIO[T]) = {
  import State._
  val regData = Reg(gen)
  val regState = RegInit(idleA)
  a.ready := regState === idleA
  b.ready := regState === idleB

  switch(regState) {
    is (idleA) {
      when (a.valid) {
        regData := a.bits
        regState := hasA
      }.otherwise {
        regState := idleB
      }
    }
    is (idleB) {
      when (b.valid) {
        regData := b.bits
        regState := hasB
      }.otherwise {
        regState := idleA
      }
    }
    is (hasA) {
      when (out.ready) {
        regState := idleB
      }
    }
    is (hasB) {
      when (out.ready) {
        regState := idleA
      }
    }
  }

  val out = Wire(new DecoupledIO(gen))
  out.valid := (regState === hasA || regState
    === hasB)
  out.bits := regData
  out
}
```

Listing 4. A fair 2-to-1 arbitration function for the `Arbiter` class.

language [7]. The XML-based source language is used to model generic CGRA architectures, limiting the implementation effort of the highly regular architectures. The hierarchical depth and IO of modules described in the source language are not known a priori as certain basic elements needed for other purposes in the flow are translated to ports in hardware. This implies the underlying hardware generation flow must be capable not only of building arbitrarily deep module hierarchies but also of supporting interfaces generated during elaboration, as higher-level modules can inherit ports from sub-modules. The proposed flow manages both these with a combination of functional, object-oriented, and imperative programming

```

class PortRecord[T <: Data](
  elts: Seq[(String, T)]
) extends Record {
  elts.map(_._2).foreach(requireIsChiselType(_))
  val elements =
    immutable.ListMap(elts.map(_._1.cloneType):_*)
}

// The below is encapsulated in a Module
val _ips = mutable.HashMap.empty[String, UInt]
val _ops = mutable.HashMap.empty[String, UInt]

lazy val io = IO(new Bundle {
  val ins = Input(new PortRecord[UInt](
    _ips.toSeq.sortBy(_._1)))
  val outs = Output(new PortRecord[UInt](
    _ops.toSeq.sortBy(_._1)))
})

```

Listing 5. An implementation of software-defined IO.

features, generating composite modules as follows:

- 1) Name the module using Chisel’s desiredName API.
- 2) Recursively create all sub-modules and add them to the current module.
- 3) Create all ports and add them to the current module.
- 4) Connect current module and sub-module ports.

The elaboration-time IO is maintained in a pair of mutable.HashMap[String, UInt] fields that are converted into Chisel Records during elaboration, as shown in Listing 5. These maps must be fully specified before any of the resulting record elements are referenced, hence why the io field is marked lazy. However, as all modules share a common parent class, the potential inheritance of ports from sub-modules means this strategy clashes with the execution order of constructors in Scala. Therefore, steps 2 through 4 above are wrapped into a build method called at the beginning of the parent class’ constructor.

A reference to the io field is inserted following the call to build to ensure its elaboration. Its fields may subsequently be accessed with their names using the apply method shown above. To the best of the authors’ knowledge, this strategy was not applied outside of RocketChip’s *diplomacy* package before [6].

D. Mealy Machine Generator

All sequential circuits can be modeled as *Mealy machines*. We can use a generic generator in Chisel to describe state machines, which allows us to evaluate different designs quickly. A Mealy machine can be defined by two functions: stateFun and outFun. Those functions are based on the current input and the machine’s internal state and describe the transition of the machine’s state to a new state and the generated output of the machine, respectively.

The Chisel module in Listing 6 is parameterized over the internal state type S, the type of accepted inputs I, and the type of the machine’s output O. The code makes use of the functional features of Chisel and Scala and takes the aforementioned

```

class Mealy[S <: Data, I <: Data, O <: Data](
  initState: S,
  genIn: I,
  genOut: O,
  stateFun: (S, I) => S,
  outFun: (S, I) => O
) extends Module {
  val io = IO(new Bundle {
    val in = Input(genIn)
    val out = Output(genOut)
  })

  val state = RegInit(initState)
  state := stateFun(state, io.in)
  io.out := outFun(state, io.in)
}

```

Listing 6. A Mealy machine generator.

```

def cntMealy(n: Int) = {
  val initState = 0.U(log2Ceil(n + 1).W)

  def cntOutput(n: Int)(s: UInt, i: Bool):
    Bool = {
      Mux(i, s === n.U, false.B)
    }

  def cntState(n: Int)(s: UInt, i: Bool):
    UInt = {
      Mux(i, Mux(s < n.U, s + 1.U, s), 0.U)
    }

  new Mealy(initState, Bool(), Bool(),
    cntState(n), cntOutput(n))
}

```

Listing 7. Code generating a Mealy machine for detecting n consecutive 1’s.

functions as parameters of the module. The implementation of the machine is trivial and consists of three lines only, two of which are function applications. The parameters genIn and genOut are not *value* parameters in the sense that they contain a concrete number but are Chisel types that are used to generically define the input and output ports of the module.

To implement a simple circuit that outputs a 1 after n consecutive 1’s have been received, one only has to specify the state transition and output functions. The code in Listing 7 makes use of a Scala feature: multiple parameter lists (also called *currying*). This allows defining the cntOutput function in such a way that cntOutput(4) creates a function that takes a UInt (the internal state) and a Bool (the current input) and decides whether to emit a 1 (the internal state is larger than 4) or not. This function is then used to instantiate the Mealy machine.

E. Hardware-Software Codesign

Many digital circuits are programmable and are interfaced by a CPU. System-on-Chip (SoC) FPGAs provide a platform for implementing such circuits, typically denoted accelerators. Implementing the interface between software and hardware can

be tedious and repetitive and will often be specific to a particular platform. With Chisel, the interface between software and hardware can be abstracted using the object-oriented features of Scala. Fpga-tidbits [14] is an example of an object-oriented framework for simplifying such hardware-software co-design.

VII. RELATED WORK

A. Generator Languages and Tools

The field of hardware generators is developing rapidly, with new languages and tools frequently proposed in the literature. While these languages tend to target each their particular application domain, some resemble Chisel in their generality and abstraction level. Examples of such include myHDL [12],⁵ which is embedded in Python, and SpinalHDL,⁶ which is embedded in Scala and is the most similar to Chisel. The DFiant HDL [21],⁷ which is also embedded in Scala, further aims to combine features of three development domains: dataflow, register transfer level, and event-driven, while abstracting away clocks and registers. In contrast, the Rust-based Spade language [28]⁸ targets pipelined designs and requires the designer to instantiate registers explicitly.

A language that raises the level of abstraction further is Clash [3].⁹ It is based on the fully functional language Haskell. A combinational circuit is modeled as a function $f : A \rightarrow B$, transforming the input of domain A to a result in the domain B . Clash does not impose many restrictions on the domain; the main restriction is not to use recursive or infinite data structures. This allows us to (almost) use the full power of the abstractions offered by Haskell. One example of this is the use of data types that contain values from one or another data type: `Either (Signed 8) (Unsigned 16)`. The Clash compiler automatically derives bit representations for the data.

As Haskell and, therefore, Clash only support purely functional programming, a special abstraction for synchronous sequential circuits needs to be used. The solution here is a streaming type `Signal dom a` that produces a value of type `a` in each cycle in the clock domain `dom`. Clash does not support asynchronous circuits. As Mealy machines are a common abstraction, Clash offers the `mealy` function that takes a function `f :: s -> i -> (s,o)` mapping a state and an input to a tuple of the new state and the corresponding output and then create the corresponding Mealy machine.

The Bluespec language¹⁰ distinguishes itself from the traditional HDLs by employing a fundamentally different execution model based on atomic actions rather than threads and processes [19]. Its compiler is associated with two language implementations integrated into SystemVerilog and Haskell. In either implementation, the `rule` (predicate); `action statements`; `endrule` construct (syntax may vary) is key to the description of arbitrarily complicated, possibly

synchronous sequential, actions occurring when the predicate is true. For hardware generation purposes, Bluespec also includes object-oriented features such as customizable, shared interfaces and methods.

The Kactus2 tool¹¹ facilitates and automates the integration of IP-XACT-defined hardware blocks, aiming to promote the reuse of IP cores [15], [20]. IP-XACT is an XML scheme that standardizes the description of IP cores [1]. The tool offers a GUI for handling bus connections, address mapping, and parameter configurations and generates the Verilog structure as well as the interconnection of the IP blocks. The users should provide the implementation of the IP blocks. In addition, Kactus2 verifies the correctness of the address mapping, ensuring that the interconnection and address space of all IP blocks are consistent.

The Genesis2 tool [26] enables hardware designers to write programs (or “recipes”) that guide the construction of hardware blocks based on a set of parameters and constraints specified in an XML format. The tool uses the scripting language Perl to construct Verilog code by generating and interconnecting hardware blocks, producing verification components, physical implementation directives, and files targeting the software stack (e.g., header files).

B. Applications

The Rocket processor project calls itself “The Rocket Chip Generator” and aims at generating (and testing) entire System-on-Chips (SoCs). Part of the project are Diplomacy and TileLink [6]. Diplomacy is a framework for solving the problems of negotiating parameters and integrating hardware units into a shared address space. It ensures the mutual compatibility of system endpoints and allows them to optimize themselves based on the knowledge of other endpoints. TileLink, a versatile standard for chip-scale shared-memory interconnects, uses Diplomacy in the Rocket chip generator to adapt the interconnect to different protocol requirements.

Chipyard [2] similarly lets developers express complete SoCs parameterized by CPU cores, buses, caches, accelerators, and peripherals elegantly in Chisel. Similar to the work presented in Sec. VI-C, the project uses lazy evaluation to postpone the construction of the hardware graph until all components are instantiated.

The `reactor-chisel` library¹² targets synthesis of event-triggered execution run-times into hardware [13]. This is achieved by a Chisel library that lets users instantiate the event-triggered components and their inter-dependencies. In `reactor-chisel`, the generation step is further divided into two phases. Handlers and connections are registered in a class hierarchy in the first step. Then, in the second step, the hardware graph is built by calling Chisel library functions.

There are many more examples of using Chisel (or related tools) to simplify building highly parameterized hardware designs, including RISC-V cores [16], accelerators for quantized

⁵<https://github.com/myhdl/myhdl>

⁶<https://github.com/SpinalHDL/SpinalHDL>

⁷<https://dfianthdl.github.io/>

⁸<https://spade-lang.org/>

⁹<http://www.clash-lang.org/>

¹⁰<https://github.com/B-Lang-org/bsc>

¹¹<https://github.com/kactus2/kactus2dev>

¹²<https://github.com/erlingrj/reactor-chisel>

neural networks [29], [8] or fast Fourier transforms [17], and generic networks-on-chip implementations for SoCs [30].

VIII. CONCLUSION

Chisel is a hardware construction language embedded in the general-purpose programming language Scala. Chisel constructs the digital circuit when executing a Scala program. This additional execution step is the *generator* step, where arbitrary Scala code can be executed. In this paper, we have explored this generation step and showed how Scala's object-oriented and functional programming features can be used to describe powerful hardware generators in just a few lines of code. To underline our points, we have provided several code examples and references to additional resources. We expect that the writing of hardware generators will grow more common when tools, such as Chisel and Scala, become mature and available.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Work partially supported with funding from European Union's Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL) under the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA) grant agreement No. 101123086 (Edu4Chip). Hans Jakob Damsgaard gratefully acknowledges funding from European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under the Marie Skłodowska Curie grant agreement No. 956090 (APROPOS: Approximate Computing for Power and Energy Optimisation, <http://www.apropos-itn.eu/>).

REFERENCES

- [1] IEEE Standard for IP-XACT, Standard Structure for Packaging, Integrating, and Reusing IP within Tool Flows. *IEEE Std 1685-2022 (Revision of IEEE Std 1685-2014)*, pages 1–750, 2023.
- [2] Alon Amid, David Biancolin, Abraham Gonzalez, Daniel Grubb, Sagar Karandikar, Harrison Liew, Albert Magyar, Howard Mao, Albert Ou, Nathan Pemberton, Paul Rigge, Colin Schmidt, John Wright, Jerry Zhao, Yakun Sophia Shao, Krste Asanović, and Borivoje Nikolić. Chipyard: Integrated Design, Simulation, and Implementation Framework for Custom SoCs. *IEEE Micro*, 40(4):10–21, 2020.
- [3] Christiaan Baaij, Matthijs Kooijman, Jan Kuper, Arjan Boeijink, and Marco Gerards. Clash: Structural Descriptions of Synchronous Hardware using Haskell. In *2010 13th Euromicro Conference on Digital System Design: Architectures, Methods and Tools*, pages 714–721. IEEE, 2010.
- [4] Jonathan Bachrach, Huy Vo, Brian Richards, Yunsup Lee, Andrew Waterman, Rimas Avizienis, John Wawrzynek, and Krste Asanovic. Chisel: Constructing Hardware in a Scala Embedded Language. In *The 49th Annual Design Automation Conference (DAC 2012)*, pages 1216–1225, San Francisco, CA, USA, June 2012. ACM.
- [5] S Alexander Chin, Noriaki Sakamoto, Allan Rui, Jim Zhao, Jin Hee Kim, Yuko Hara-Azumi, and Jason Anderson. CGRA-ME: A Unified Framework for CGRA Modelling and Exploration. In *2017 IEEE 28th international conference on application-specific systems, architectures and processors (ASAP)*, pages 184–189. IEEE, 2017.
- [6] Henry Cook, Wesley Terpstra, and Yunsup Lee. Diplomatic Design Patterns: A TileLink Case Study. In *1st Workshop on Computer Architecture Research with RISC-V*, volume 23, 2017.
- [7] Hans Jakob Damsgaard, Aleksandr Ometov, and Jari Nurmi. Generating CGRA Processing Element Hardware with CGRAgen. In *2023 26th Euromicro Conference on Digital System Design (DSD)*, pages 1–7. IEEE, 2023.
- [8] Hasan Genc, Seah Kim, Alon Amid, Ameer Haj-Ali, Vighnesh Iyer, Pranav Prakash, Jerry Zhao, Daniel Grubb, Harrison Liew, Howard Mao, et al. Gemini: Enabling Systematic Deep-Learning Architecture Evaluation via Full-Stack Integration. In *2021 58th ACM/IEEE Design Automation Conference (DAC)*, pages 769–774. IEEE, 2021.
- [9] IEEE Computer Society. *IEEE Standard for SystemVerilog: Unified Hardware Design, Specification and Verification Language*, 2005.
- [10] IEEE Computer Society. *IEEE Standard for Verilog Hardware Description Language*, 2006.
- [11] IEEE Computer Society. *IEEE Standard VHDL Language Reference Manual*, 2009.
- [12] Keerthan Jaic and Melissa C Smith. Enhancing Hardware Design Flows with myHDL. In *2015 ACM/SIGDA International Symposium on Field-Programmable Gate Arrays*, pages 28–31, 2015.
- [13] Erling Rennemo Jellum, Martin Schoeberl, Edward Ashford Lee, and Milica Orlandic. Codesign of reactor-oriented hardware and software for cyber-physical systems. *ACM Trans. Reconfigurable Technol. Syst.*, jun 2024. Just Accepted.
- [14] Erling Rennemo Jellum, Yaman Umuruglu, Milica Orlandic, and Martin Schoeberl. fpga-tidbits: Rapid Prototyping of FPGA Accelerators in Chisel. In *2023 26th Euromicro Conference on Digital System Design (DSD)*, pages 153–160. IEEE, 2023.
- [15] Antti Kamppi, Esko Pekkarinen, Janne Virtanen, Joni-Matti Määttä, Juho Järvinen, Lauri Matilainen, Mikko Teuvo, and Timo D. Hämäläinen. Kactus2: A Graphical EDA Tool Built on the IP-XACT Standard. *Journal of Open Source Software*, 2(13):151, 2017.
- [16] Yunsup Lee, Andrew Waterman, Henry Cook, Brian Zimmer, Ben Keller, Alberto Puggelli, Jaehwa Kwak, Ruzica Jevtic, Stevo Bailey, Milovan Blagojevic, et al. An Agile Approach to Building RISC-V Microprocessors. *IEEE Micro*, 36(2):8–20, 2016.
- [17] V. M. Milovanović and M. L. Petrović. A Highly Parametrizable Chisel HCL Generator of Single-Path Delay Feedback FFT Processors. In *2019 IEEE 31st International Conference on Microelectronics (MIEL)*, pages 247–250, 2019.
- [18] Shahid Ali Murtza, Osman Hasan, and Kashif Saghar. Vertgen: An Automatic Verilog Testbench Generator for Generic Circuits. In *2016 International Conference on Emerging Technologies (ICET)*, pages 1–5. IEEE, 2016.
- [19] Rishiyur S Nikhil and Arvind. What is Bluespec? *ACM SIGDA Newsletter*, 39(1):1–1, 2009.
- [20] Esko Pekkarinen and Timo D. Hämäläinen. Modeling RISC-V Processor in IP-XACT. In *2018 21st Euromicro Conference on Digital System Design (DSD)*, pages 140–147, 2018.
- [21] Oron Port and Yoav Etsion. Registerless Hardware Description. 2021.
- [22] Martin Schoeberl. Lipsi: Probably the Smallest Processor in the World. In *Architecture of Computing Systems – ARCS 2018*, pages 18–30. Springer International Publishing, 2018.
- [23] Martin Schoeberl. *Digital Design with Chisel*. Kindle Direct Publishing, 2019. available at <https://github.com/schoeberl/chisel-book>.
- [24] Martin Schoeberl and Morten Borup Petersen. Leros: The Return of the Accumulator Machine. In Martin Schoeberl, Thilo Pionteck, Sascha Uhrig, Jürgen Brehm, and Christian Hochberger, editors, *Architecture of Computing Systems - ARCS 2019 - 32nd International Conference, Proceedings*, pages 115–127. Springer, May 2019.
- [25] Ofer Shacham. *Chip Multiprocessor Generator: Automatic Generation of Custom and Heterogeneous Compute Platforms*. Stanford University, 2011.
- [26] Ofer Shacham. *Chip Multiprocessor Generator: Automatic Generation of Custom and Heterogeneous Compute Platforms*. Phd thesis, Stanford University, 2011.
- [27] Ofer Shacham, Omid Azizi, Megan Wachs, Wajahat Qadeer, Zain Asgar, Kyle Kelley, John P Stevenson, Stephen Richardson, Mark Horowitz, Benjamin Lee, et al. Rethinking Digital Design: Why Design Must Change. *IEEE micro*, 30(6):9–24, 2010.
- [28] Frans Skarman and Oscar Gustafsson. Spade: An HDL Inspired by Modern Software Languages. In *2022 32nd International Conference on Field-Programmable Logic and Applications (FPL)*, pages 454–455. IEEE, 2022.
- [29] Jure Vreča and Anton Biasizzo. Towards Deploying Highly Quantized Neural Networks on FPGA Using Chisel. In *2023 26th Euromicro Conference on Digital System Design (DSD)*, pages 161–167. IEEE, 2023.
- [30] Jerry Zhao, Animesh Agrawal, Borivoje Nikolic, and Krste Asanović. Constellation: An Open-Source SoC-Capable NoC Generator. In *2022 15th IEEE/ACM International Workshop on Network on Chip Architectures (NoCArc)*, pages 1–7, 2022.